

FEED VALUE CHAIN IN LIVESTOCK SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN

Sirojiddin Eshmatov

(DSc in agricultural economics) International Agriculture University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15179976>

Аннотация. Чорвачиликни ривожланишида бир қанча омилар билан бирга чорвани йилнинг турли фасларида сифатли озуқа билан етарлича таъминлаш ҳамда озуқа манбаларини кенгайтириш муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Бу уларни махсуддорлигини оширишга, турли касалликларга чалинишини олдини олишга, соғлом насл беришга, бутун қиймат занжири бўйлаб иштирокчилар даромадлари ўсишига ва пировардида якуний истеъмолчиларни сифатли махсулотлар билан таъминлаш имкони яратади. Ушбу мақолада чорвалик қиймат занжирининг озуқа босқичи ҳолати олиб борилган изланишлар натижаси тўғрисида фикр юритилади.

Калит сўзлар: майдо шохли чорва, чорва озуқаси, қиймат занжири.

Аннотация. В развитии животноводства, наряду с рядом факторов, важным является обеспечение скота достаточным количеством качественных кормов в разное время года и расширение источников кормов. Это позволит повысить их продуктивность, предотвратить заражение различными заболеваниями, получить здоровое потомство, увеличить доходы участников всей цепочки создания стоимости и в конечном итоге обеспечить конечных потребителей качественной продукцией. В данной статье рассматриваются результаты исследований, проведенных по состоянию кормового этапа цепочки создания стоимости в животноводстве.

Ключевые слова: мелкий рогатый скот, корм, цепочки добавленной стоимости.

Annotation. In the development of livestock farming, along with a number of factors, it is important to provide livestock with sufficient quality feed at different times of the year and expand feed sources. This will increase their productivity, prevent them from contracting various diseases, produce healthy offspring, increase the income of participants throughout the value chain, and ultimately provide end consumers with quality products. This article discusses the results of research conducted on the state of the feed stage of the livestock value chain.

Key words: small ruminants, livestock feed, value chain.

INTRODUCTION

Considering one of the key economic subsectors Uzbekistan's economy, livestock constitutes 15.5 percent of the GDP and about 50.8 percent (livestock value added) of the national agricultural GDP¹. Livestock is considered one of the main sources of the rural households' income and plays a significant role for food and nutrition security. Livestock farming is also considered an important source of self-employment for the rural population, especially for rural women. In 2019, the number of people employed in livestock and livestock derived jobs in Uzbekistan is 420 thousand where it is expected to be 706.0 thousand units in 2030 (Khujabekov et al., 2023). Dairy (cattle), meat (cattle, small ruminants, poultry, and fish),

¹ National Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan, 2025

and egg (poultry) are the most important livestock value chains (Romagnoli et al., 2022). According to the results of 2024, peasant and private households have the highest shares in livestock production, in particular, they account for 84.6% of meat, 92.5% of milk, 57.0% of eggs, 81.9% of wool, and 79.3% of karakul leather². Most of the livestock is kept in households — 76% of cattle, 78% of goats and sheep, 53% of poultry (Review.uz, 2022).

Despite the reforms carried out in recent years to improve livestock breeding, expand feed resources, ensure animal health, and widely introduce market principles into the sector, a number of problems can be identified that hinder the development of the livestock value chain. In particular, they include: 1) difficulty in accessing financing sources (loans up to 24% and short terms), lack of systematization of the system for combating various diseases (losses and low productivity as a result of the spread of diseases), feed problems (severe degradation of pastures, very limited types of pasture fodder, low cultivation of fodder crops, high prices of processed fodder products), limited processing industry (products such as hides and wool are discarded without processing, destroying potential income), lack of knowledge and skills in livestock farming, etc.. Among these groups of limiting factors, problems related to livestock feed are of leading importance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Key factors constraining livestock production in Uzbekistan include insufficient feed resources and lack of land area (Hoek, 2020). Feed availability is one of the key issues of livestock rearing in Uzbekistan. Modest sizes of dehkan plots restrain provision of feeds for livestock, which is bred in dehkan households. Only 57% of households supply (even partially) their livestock with feeds produced on their own plots. The majority (75%) of them have to buy feeds (Yu.B. Yusupov et al., 2010). Moreover, 62% of households deals with collecting feeds for their livestock - mow grass, collect food waste etc. Grazing livestock along roadsides and ditches is widespread. Grazing livestock on community pastures, including by hired shepherds, is not common due to a lack of rangelands. As the population grows, the demand for livestock products, such as meat and dairy products, increases. In order to increase the efficiency of livestock farming, it is very important to increase the material and technical capabilities of farms specializing in the production of livestock feed in the regions. Cattle on the farm showed extra growth of 80.3 kg when fed a regular feed ration and 95.8 kg when fed feed supplemented with feed additives (Toshboev et al., 2024). Cattle diets were mainly based on crop residues (stover, straw) and cattle mortality due to cold stress represents a threat to animal welfare. A recent USDA report (2011), for example, underlined that insufficient feed resources and lack of land areas and turnover are key factors affecting negatively the livestock sector in Uzbekistan. Nevertheless, the generalization of such bottlenecks on livestock or cattle production is insufficient for shaping and developing policies to improve livestock management, production and productivity (Siegmond-Schultze et al., 2013). The small farmers, called dekhans, do not have enough space to feed their animals on their own plot of land, usually a half-hectare adjoining their home. Yet, despite limited resources and high levels of poverty, the dekhans provide 90% of the national meat and dairy production (AFD, 2022). Sheep farming is one of the oldest branches of livestock farming in Central Asia including Uzbekistan where the local breed of Karakul sheep is not only a source of Karakul skins, which are its main product, but also serves as a basis for producing meat, wool, and leather products at low costs. The development of sheep farming is a socio-economic issue and has become one of the priority areas for

² Annual Yearbook 2024. National Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan, 2025

deepening and advancing economic reforms in the sector (Akhmedov, 2024). Regardless of allocation of 0.30-0.40 hectares of land were allocated for each type of commodity for the fodder base, the monitoring of the land use is not well organized. The structure of the placement of feed crops should be focused on obtaining at least 18-19 tons of feed units per ha by the selection of varieties, by agrotechnical methods, ensuring optimal normalization with organic (20-30 tons) and mineral fertilizers (Dosmukhamedova, 2022). One of the most serious problems is the shortage of feed is associated with an excessive reduction in the sowing areas (by 70% since 1991) of feed crops. Small-scale livestock farms have limited access to land and face difficulties to supply their animals with seasonal feed in winter when feed prices are high in the market. As per conducted survey results, 43.2% of respondents would like to use more land for pasture land where 93.7% mentioned the lack of pasture land to rent (Khamdamova et al., 2024). Grazing on public pastures, including by hired herders, is not very common due to a lack of grazing land. High pressure associated with excessive number of livestock grazing, climate change and noncompliance with pasture management are main causes led to a deterioration in the quality of pastures. The main causes of pasture degradation are wind, water erosion, as well as hillside plowing, improper irrigation practices and excessive grazing (Faizullaev, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted based on primary field data (quantitative and qualitative) collected through questionnaire among value chain participants and secondary census data in addition to literature review relevant to the livestock value chain. Primary data for the study was collected on the example of different regions of Uzbekistan. Field survey with value chain actors was conducted in Samarkand and Kashkadarya regions. Primary data is collected in value chains including farmers, livestock clusters/LLC, dehqan farms and households. Secondary data sources included National Statistics Committee and Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Data collection tools are household survey, target group interviews, expert discussions and observations, official annual reports and other relevant publications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sources of feed of sheep and goat in the sites

In Samarkand and Kashkadarya regions, where the survey was conducted, and in Tashkent, Khorezm regions, and Fergana Valley regions, where sheep value chain experiences were studied, there are certain differences in terms of geographic location, climatic conditions, and sheep rearing practices. In general, due to a number of other similar factors, the sources of fodder for sheep are different in the regions of Uzbekistan.

Dependence of small ruminant feeds on different sources in the regions

Regions	Desert Pasture	Mountain Pasture	Own feed crops	Purchased wholesale	Retail market	Grazing in edges of ditch, field	SR share in total country
Kashkadarya	High	Very high	Medium	Low	High	High	20.8%
Samarkand	High	High	High	High	Medium	Medium	11.0%
Surkhandarya	High	Very high	High	Medium	Medium	High	10.7%
Bukhara	very high	Very Low	Medium	High	Low	Low	10.2%
Navoi	very high	Very high	Very low	Low	Medium	High	10.1%
Jizzakh	High	Very high	Very high	Very high	High	Low	9.8%
Andijan	Not exist	Very low	Very low	Very high	High	Very low	6.5%
Karakalpak	very high	Not exist	Low	High	High	Medium	5.1%

Tashkent	Low	High	High	High	Medium	Low	4.7%
Fergana	Not exist	Medium	Very low	Very high	High	Very low	3.9%
Namangan	Not exist	Low	Very low	Very high	High	Very low	3.5%
Khorezm	very high	Not exist	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	2.1%
Syrdarya	very high	Not exist	High	High	Medium	Medium	1.6%

N/E-not exist; SR-small ruminants; *Source: Author's observation*

In the survey areas, shepherds graze sheep mainly in pastures from early spring to mid-autumn. In winter sheep herders use hay and other types of fodder collected during the summer. In order to ensure the health of the sheep during the cold days of winter, they are also fed with additional concentrate feeds. Big farms use grain from their own farming while small-scale herders mainly purchase feed and grains from local feed market.

Hay storage (hay shed) in a sheep farm, Kashkadarya region

Camel's thorn hay storage (open air) in dehkan farm, Samarkand region

Hay storage of sheep herders in the surveyed regions.

©Photo/Sirojiddin Eshmatov

Cotton seed husk, cotton seed hulls obtained from cotton cleaning and processing plants are used as fodder for sheep. Also, cottonseed meal, sunflower meal, sesame/flax meal, peanut husks and other types of wastes from grain mills are used as additional ingredients for small ruminant feed.

Fodder types and their characteristics

All types of fodder for sheep are mainly divided into three groups (Agro-Olam.Uz, 2021): i) feed made from plant products; ii) feed products made from animals; iii) mineral substances. Feeds from plant products are:

1. Green grasses- natural pasture grasses, hayfields, planted grasses and others
2. Course/Roughage (feed)- hay, straw, grain extracted corn stalk
3. Roots- beets and turnips
4. Ensiled feed- silage
5. Multi grain mixed feeds- grains and seeds
6. Technical production waste- waste (feed) from flour industry, sugar factories, fruit/vegetable processing, and oil production enterprises).

Feed from animals include bone meal, fish meal where Mineral substances include different chemical additives and vitamins.

Hydroponics (greenfeed) feeding. Due to factors such as climate change, limited water resources, lack of fodder base for sheep and goats, low quality of fodder, dwindling pastures, high prices of fodder, hydroponics, which is environmentally safe, high-quality, cheap and resource-efficient fodder cultivation, is increasing. Sheep and goat breeders are also very interested in it.

Greenfeed is produced in five to eight days following the following five steps:

1. Wheat seeds are washed
2. Humid seeds are stored in closed barrels for one to two days
3. Seeds are placed on trays in the hydroponic room
4. Seeds are irrigated every three hours by means of a rain irrigation.

Greenfeed growing in hydroponic method

©Photo/Sirojiddin Eshmatov

Groundwater is used which is low cost with no supply shortage. The use of groundwater is also important to ensure stable water quality in areas where surface water is often saline. One of the surveyed farmers grows feed for 5 days (outturn of 4 kg of feed from 1 kg of wheat) while the other does for 8 days (outturn of 5.6 kg of feed from 1 kg of wheat).

5. Once fully grown, green feed is cut in small pieces (mixed with wheat bran) and fed to sheep and goats. Sheep herders mention that greenfeed has a high caloric content per feed unit and increases animal productivity.

Demand for greenfeed is high and has potential to grow when the product becomes more known. Livestock farms and fish farms located in the regions of Uzbekistan are the main potential buyers of greenfeed. Some product preferences are already shaping-up with livestock farms interested in purchasing 5-day grown greenfeed (high energy content) while fish farms are interested in purchasing 8-day grown feed (high biomass).

Cost comparison of green feed and traditional feeds

	Green feed*	Wheat bran	Corn bran	Dried alfalfa hay**	Wheat straw***
Cost (UZS/ton)	2,000,000 (\$162)	3,200,000 (\$260)	3,800 000 (\$310)	2,400,000 (\$195)	1,500,000 (\$122)
Daily consumption per sheep, kg	3.0	2.5	2.5	7.0	7.0
Daily cost per sheep, UZS	6,000 (\$0.48)	8,000 (\$0.65)	9,500 (\$0.78)	16,800 (\$1.36)	10,500 (\$0.85)
Digestibility	High	Good	Good	Medium	Low
Productivity (weight gain/day)****	High	High	High	Medium	Very Low

* Selling price; **One bale of dried alfalfa is 15 kg and price is UZS 35,000.0 /bale.

***Average weight of one bale of wheat straw is 10 kg and rice is UZS 18,000.0/bale.

****based on survey data and interviews with key informants

Source: survey field data

Since the technology of greenfeed preparation by hydroponics method is innovative, it is appropriate to organize trainings for increasing the capacity of farmers, dehkans as well as households.

Availability/Scarcity of feed over seasons

One of the biggest problems of sheep herders in Uzbekistan is the shortage of fodder. This shortage is caused by a number of factors. Seasonally, from late fall to early spring, sheep breeders experience the most difficult forage supply period. As mentioned above, if farms with large arable areas reserve their fodder crops for the winter months in the form of hay or grain, farmers and households are forced to buy fodder at a high price during the winter months. In rural areas, winter feed stocks are mostly purchased from farmers and wholesalers, while in urban areas, this task is mostly done by retailers in local feed markets. Respondents who took part in the survey stated that there is a severe shortage of fodder in the winter months, but they said that they cover the demand for fodder products from various sources.

Supply of fodder for sheep herders in winter months

Source

: Survey data

Most of the sheep herders (35%) stock feed and raw materials for the winter months in advance. Such an approach allows to save a certain amount of financial resources due to the purchase of more products at a cheaper time in the summer and autumn months before the winter. Also, buying in advance ensures quality products and avoids the risk of food becoming unavailable during the winter months. A certain number of sheep herders (3%) sell their sheep in winter due to the lack of warm indoor sheep houses to keep sheep in winter months, lack of fodder stock, lack of funds to care for sheep and the need of people to improve their family supply in winter. During the survey, it was found that only 10% of sheep herders (mainly farms and dehkans) grow plants that they use for feed and stocking for winter on their land. The survey did not explore the factors preventing this in depth. On the contrary, the reasons for this have been thoroughly studied in literature review.

Reasons restraining dehkans, households and farms in producing feed crops

Source: adopted from Yusupov et al, 2010.

Dehkan farms and households suffer from insufficiency of feeds for the sheep production because of lack of land and low feed crop productivity. As a result of water scarcity, the cultivation of food crops is becoming a problem, and the installation of water-saving technologies is expensive for small-scale farms and dehkan farms. Another factor is administrative restrictions which farmers and dehkan farms are not allowed to choose types of crops to cultivate, which are actually pushed out with cotton, wheat and fruits and vegetables. Gross harvest of main feed crops including barley and corn are not increasing because of above mentioned factors in Uzbekistan. Cotton meal, wheat bran, low-quality or non-edible vegetables are also used as fodder for sheep, and certain increases are observed in the cultivation of these products.

Grazing distance in long range pastures.

Sheep grazed on pastures in mountain and desert areas can graze 8-10 km in 1 day. The size of these pastures, the large number of sheep, the condition of the green mass in the pastures, certain requirements for the preservation of pastures and other factors are the reason for this arrangement.

A farmer who rents a pasture at a distance of up to 400 km (from Samarkand-Almaliq district to Tashkent region) pays 30,000.0 UZS for 1 sheep to transport to take sheep to the pasture and bring them back. Trucks of various types are usually used to transport sheep over this distance.

Payment for grazing. Farms hire shepherds to graze their sheep on leased pastures and pay 3,000.0 UZS per month per sheep. Pasture rent farmers pay 110,000.0 UZS per year for 1 sheep (grazing period for 9 months). Households and dehkan farms (with a small number of sheep) pay 15,000.0 UZS per month for pasture rent per sheep, depending on their location in different areas. In the summer months, sheep rest in the pasture for 3-4 hours during the day. At this time they are also watered. At night, it is fully grazed and free-fed. Also, the fields where cotton, corn, wheat, barley, mung beans (mush), melons, and other types of crops are harvested for sheep feeding are also rented.

IN CASE OF SHEEP FARM. It was studied that large farmers reserve 150 kg of hay per sheep for the winter months (for 90 days) except for grazing. For example, buying dried Alhagi costs around 400.0 UZS per 1 kg. As an additional feed, 0.5 kg of barley per day is given to keep the sheep healthy from the winter (on average, one sheep consumes

150,000.0 UZS of barley during the whole winter). Mostly women are hired to harvest carrack in summer and Alhagi in autumn to stock up for winter. The number of women hired for these jobs can reach 40 and they work 60-90 days a year. They are paid 80,000.0 UZS per day for their work.

Sheep grazing varies depending on types of sheep herders, their economic condition and location, the number of sheep in the flock, the quality of the pastures, the supply of feed and fodder products, and other factors.

IN CASE OF THE SHEEP CLUSTER OPERATING IN SAMARKAND REGION

General info: The total land area owned is 44,000.0 hectares (25,000 hectares of leased land) and the total number of small ruminants is over 13,000 head. Number of goats in the flock is slightly more than 1,000 heads. The number of herds has decreased in the last 3 years due to lack of fodder and pasture, marketing issues of meat, leather and wool. Total number of workers is 62, of which six are women. The number of members of the cluster is 17 sheep farms.

Grazing distance: Although it has its own pasture, it sends sheep to other remote areas to graze due to low rainfall and low species of forage plants in the pastures. During the year, the cluster grazes sheep over a total distance of more than 1,200 km from its location - Navoi region (Uchkuduk, Tomdi, Nurota, Zarafshan districts) - Bukhara region (Karavulbazar) - Jizzakh region (Forish, Zomin districts).

Types of grazing areas and grazing fees: Small ruminants are grazed in the following areas in different regions: Kattakurgan district, Samarkand region (on harvested cotton fields), Jizzakh region (on mountain pastures and harvested grain fields), Navoi and Bukhara regions (on desert pastures).

Grazing in desert pastures - 25,000.0 UZS (USD 2.0)/per sheep;

Grazing in wheat harvested field - 50,000.0 UZS (USD 4.0)/per sheep;

Grazing in cotton harvested field - 30,000.0 UZS (USD 2.4)/per sheep;

Transportation of sheep to pastures: Sheep are transported to pastures in the regions in large trucks. 180-190 sheep are transported in one truck and the transportation cost for 300 km one way is UZS 3,500,000.0 (USD 280.0).

During the winter months, farms allow farmers and households to graze their sheep on their winter wheat fields. Sheep eat the sprouted parts of the wheat, the barley roots will grow stronger, and the strong winds and rains of the spring will not blow them to the ground.

Household small ruminants grazing in and around ditches in fields.

Sheep grazing in fields of winter barley.

Grazing of small ruminants on cultivated fields in winter months. ©Photo/ Eshmatov

This opportunity is mainly in January-February. With the onset of spring, grazing of livestock is not allowed on the fields planted with wheat.

Challenges related to feed and feeding

During the survey, 75% sheep breeders reported that the number of sheep they own decreased in the last 3 years, about 3% reported that the number did not change, and the remaining 22% reported that the number of sheep increased. The reasons why the number of sheep decreased or did not change were studied and it was found that various factors influence this.

Factors hindering the increase in the number of sheep

Factors	Decreased	Constant	Increase
	75%	3%	22%
Financial issues	A	A	C
Lack of feed and pasture	A	A	A
Lack of sheep housing in winter	C	B	D
Lack of time	D	D	D
Other	High cost, Low margin	Selling issues, Diseases	Diseases

Factors’ effect level: A-strong, B-Moderate, C-Low, D-No effect

Source: Survey data

There are a number of fodder-related problems, such as poor pasture quality and fodder sources, interruptions in fodder supply, shortage of fodder products in different seasons, high cost of fodder products (especially in winter), and lack of quality nutritious crop planting practices across the country. The salinity level is increasing in the land areas where food and other main agricultural crops are grown. As a result, this is an obstacle to increasing the land area for planting nutritious crops for livestock. It is becoming difficult to feed small ruminants in the desert and sub-mountain regions with the decrease in the quality of the pastures.

The following negative trends in desert pastures are occurring in the surveyed areas:

- pastures are decreasing due to strong degradation;
- plant species are disappearing due to low rainfall and lack of irrigation;
- financial problems of farms in plowing pastures, irrigation and organizing other types of infrastructures are increasing;
- long-term grazing of more than normal number of sheep in wet pastures makes the soil denser;
- precipitation does not soak into the soil, and as a result, the growth of plants with deep roots and long vegetation slows down;
- water erosion occurs, ravines appear;
- pastures can be used only in spring, and in summer, plants do not grow;
- these result in the growth of grass-forming plants and this is a sign of degradation. Soil erosion can lead to the loss of valuable topsoil, which is essential for plant growth;
- only root-propagating plants will grow and seed-propagating plants will decrease. This is considered a negative indicator.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is necessary to strengthen the effective use of pastures, their control and measures to combat degradation. It is very important to systematically carry out scientific research on the

state of vegetation cover in pastures, the trend of degradation processes, the study of the economic potential of pastures and the development of a system of rational use of pastures on this basis. It is necessary to review the system of training specialists in the field, develop education and training programs based on foreign experiences, and solve the problem of staff shortage on this basis. Establishment of forest plantations in desert and semi-desert areas, strengthening of rehabilitation of pastures in crisis, and expansion of special programs aimed at preventing the increase of soil erosion and dust formation under the influence of wind are considered important directions. Excavation of shaft and vertical wells, construction and reconstruction of pumping stations in the areas of high water shortage pastures on the principle of public and private partnership will also bring long-term positive results.

REFERENCES

1. AFD, 2022. Promoting a Greener, More Robust Livestock Sector in Uzbekistan. <https://www.afd.fr/en/actualites/promoting-greener-more-robust-livestock-sector-uzbekistan> (accessed 3.22.25).
2. Agro-Olam.Uz, 2021. Чорвачиликда озуқа ресурслари ва уларнинг таснифланиши. <https://agro-olam.uz/chorvachilikda-ozuqa-resurslari-va-ularning-tasniflanishi/> (accessed 3.22.25).
3. Akhmedov, B.A., 2024. THE STATE AND CHALLENGES OF SHEEP FARMING IN UZBEKISTAN. Web of Agriculture: Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences 2, 102–105.
4. Dosmukhamedova, M.H., 2022. Development factors of the state of the livestock sector in Uzbekistan. IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 1068, 012034. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1068/1/012034>
5. Faizullaev, M., 2022. The main characteristics of the development of the livestock network in the republic of Uzbekistan.
6. Khamdamova, N., Ulmasova, O., Xudayberdiyeva, M., 2024. Livestock Development Problems and Prospects in Uzbekistan. Green Economy and Development 2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12745717>
7. Khujabekov, A., Tesfaye, T., Kertaev, A., 2023. Supporting Effective Jobs Lending at Scale: The Case of Uzbekistan Livestock Sector Development Project (LSDP).
8. Review.uz, 2022. The livestock sector of Uzbekistan in the dynamics of development. <https://review.uz/en/post/ozbekistonda-chorvachilik-tarmogining-rivojlanish-dinamikasi> (accessed 3.22.25).
9. Romagnoli, S., Faustino, A., Adilov, S., Arney, D., Guidi, A., Paluanov, B., Yulchiev, J., Xasanov, S.H., Abdurasulovich, I.Z., 2022. Uzbekistan: a report on livestock production and the provision of veterinary services. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
10. Siegmund-Schultze, M., Rischkowsky, B., Yuldashev, I., Abdalniyazov, B., Lamers, J.P.A., 2013. The emerging small-scale cattle farming sector in Uzbekistan: Highly integrated with crop production but suffering from low productivity. Journal of Arid Environments 98, 93–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2013.08.001>
11. Toshboev, A., Siddikov, Z., Narinbaeva, G., Muratova, M., 2024. Increasing efficiency of livestock farming in Uzbekistan. E3S Web Conf. 563, 03098. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202456303098>